

Study of Ion-Solvent Interaction in Ethylene Carbonate from Viscosity Data

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Ion-solvent interaction of some tetraalkylammonium and common ions in ethylene carbonate (EC) has been studied from the viscosity data in this communication. The study indicates that the tetraalkylammonium ions are not solvated while the common ions are and their solvation appears to vary inversely as the radius of the ion; the structure of the solvent appears to remain unaffected beyond the solvation layer in presence of these ions.

IN continuation with the earlier studies on ion-solvent interaction of the tetraalkylammonium and alkali metal halides in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO)^{1,2} and propylene carbonate(PC)^{3,4}, the work has now been extended to ethylene carbonate (EC) which, although is similar to these liquids in having no hydrogen-bonding interaction, has a high dielectric constant (85.81)⁵ which would ensure complete ionization of electrolytes when dissolved in it. It has also a considerable liquid range. Although some studies on viscosity of electrolytes have been reported⁶, a detailed investigation is still lacking. It is proposed to undertake a study of ionsolvent interaction of some tetraalkylammonium and common salts from the point of view of viscosity in this communication.

Experimental

Ethylene carbonate (Fluka, purum) was fractionally crystallised three times and the sample thus obtained was distilled under reduced pressure. The middle fraction of the distillate was collected in a dark coloured bottle and kept in a dry box. The sample was found to melt sharply at 36.5° and its electrical conductance was of the order of 10⁻⁸ mho.

The tetraalkylammonium iodides (DPI, U.S.A.) and common salts (BDH, AR) were purified in the usual manner. Solutions were prepared on weight basis and volume concentration was obtained from the corresponding density. The experimental procedure for measuring density and viscosity, the equipment used and precautions are the same as described earlier³.

Results and Discussion

From the data thus obtained viscosity was calculated, and the specific viscosity

$\Psi = \frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0 \sqrt{C}}$ was obtained and $\Psi/\sqrt{C}$ calculated. The $\Psi/\sqrt{C}$ vs $\sqrt{C}$ curves for different salts for different temperatures were drawn.

The solute-solvent interaction in ethylene carbonate was examined using the well known Jones and Dole viscosity equation⁷, namely,

$$\frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0 \sqrt{C}} = \Psi/\sqrt{C} = A + B\sqrt{C}$$

the values of coefficient B obtained from the $\Psi/\sqrt{C}$ vs $\sqrt{C}$ plots in different cases are given in table 1.

TABLE I : B VALUES OF SALTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE IN EC

Salts	B values at			
	40°	45°	50°	55°
Me ₄ NI	0.571	0.560	0.551	0.543
Et ₄ NI	0.712	0.712	0.702	0.711
Pr ₄ NI	0.794	0.801	0.793	0.795
Bu ₄ NI	0.920	0.923	0.910	0.912
Pen ₄ NI	1.042	1.049	1.051	1.050
Hex ₄ NI	1.203	1.203	1.193	1.202
Hep ₄ NI	1.302	1.321	1.312	1.313
Lil. H ₂ O	0.850	0.804	0.770	0.750
NaI	0.821	0.801	0.791	0.750
KI	0.652	0.638	0.652	0.669
RbI	0.581	0.574	0.576	0.568

Referring to table 1, it may be observed that the effect of temperature on the B-coefficient appears to be very little in this solvent as in most other non-aqueous aprotic solvents with little or no molecular association due to the absence of hydrogen bonding in them; some

slight, erratic and haphazard changes may be ignored. Thus from the temperature independence of B it appears that the structure of the solvent remains unaffected in presence of these salts.

The variation in the value of B with the radius of the ion may next be examined to see if this would be of any help. Although this variation may be observed in table 1, it is made more explicit from Fig. 1 in which B value for salts has been plotted against radius of the cation. It may be remarked that since Γ^- is common to all these salts, variation in B with the radius may be assumed to be due to the cation only.

Fig. 1. B Vs Ionic radii plot in E.C

It may be noted from Figure 1 that for the salts containing R_4N^+ ions, B value is larger, the larger the cation which indicates that the electrostatic ion-solvent interaction, if at all, is very weak in these cases and resistance to the movement of the ion in solution depends upon the size (i.e. radius) of the bare ion only.

Reverse appears to be the case with the common salts containing small compact cations for which B decreases with the increasing size of cation. Apparently, the high charge density on the smaller cations gives rise to strong electrostatic ion-solvent interaction in solution which does not appreciably change within small temperature range of the present investigation, and hence it is not shown up as the change in the value of B when the temperature changes. The smaller the ion, the stronger the ion-solvent dipole interaction and the larger the size of the solvated ion in solution and the larger the value of B. Thus the result of this investigation lead one to conclude that while the R_4N^+ ions do not appear to be solvated in EC, the alkali metal ions are appreciably solvated, their solvation varying inversely as the radius of the cation.

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